

**SYNERGIC RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EFFECTIVE
INFORMATION AND INTELLIGENCE NEEDS ANALYSIS,
UTILIZATION AND SECURITY IN NIGERIA**

Iheriohanma, E. B. J.¹,

Emenyonu, Chinyere C.²

¹Directorate of General Studies,
Federal University of Technology,
Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

²Department of Library and Information Science,
Federal Polytechnic,
Nekede, Imo State, Nigeria

Abstract:

The general objective of the paper examines critically the synergic relationship between effective information and intelligence needs gathering, analysis and utilization in relation to security situation in Nigeria. Effective pursuit and execution of security needs in every nation depend critically on the conscious security information drive, intelligence gathering, the existence of the necessary security gadgets and apparatus, the zeal of the citizenry to be security conscious and to provide information needed, the will power of the government in place and security institutions to analyze and utilize the available information and intelligence gathered. The challenging problems of study indicate that budgetary funds are made available to security agencies and institutions yet insecurity prevails in Nigeria, lives and properties are destroyed on daily basis, foreign investors relocate out of Nigeria for fear of insecurity, inability of security agencies to pro-actively respond to security demands, seemingly government complicity in curtailing the incessant insecurity, etc. These point to the lack of information and intelligence needs gathering and analysis, lack of relevant modern ICT security equipment and personnel, sharing intelligence information and collaborative efforts among these agencies. The paper is discursive and analytical in methodology. While the paper examined the challenges faced by these agencies and reasons for their ineffectiveness, it avers that, in order to buttress security and grow the economy, the government of Nigeria should, among others, ensure that there are collaborative and effective information and intelligence drive, analysis, sharing and utilization in relation to security pursuit; high technological military hardware for surveillance should be in use; sentiments, individualism, exclusionism, ethnicity and parochialism should not be above national interest; economy should be boosted through job creation, employment, empowerment, entrepreneurship, industrialization and manufacture to mitigate the

burden on the agencies and create opportunity for individuals and institutions to explore their potentials and the economy to blossom.

Keywords: effective information needs, intelligence, information analysis, utilization, insecurity, Nigeria

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Conceptual Clarification

In personal, organizational or national settings, information is essentially a sine qua non and a derived process. It is derived from the need to effectively and efficiently create and use ideas and knowledge for reducing uncertainty in human decision-making processes towards meeting human needs, desires and visions (Aina, Mutula and Tiamiya, 2008). Uwemi (1990) in Uhegbu (2006) defines information as that which has been subjected to some processing functions capable of answering a user's quest, but recorded, summarized or simply collated and which would help in decision-making. Information is a finished product ready for use, the source and media of communication notwithstanding. In other words, information is a meaningful communication of symbols transferred between any two points in human communication or machine networks (Heets, 2004).

Uhegbu (2006) sees information as that which adds to one's awareness or understanding of some topics, issues, problems or events to which individuals in every society have access to in order to play their respective roles in the society and live meaningful and secure life. Information is data that have been collated, interpreted and understood by the recipient of the message (Unegbu & Nwanekezie, 2014). It reduces uncertainty and has value. It tells the recipient something not already known and which could not be predicted. This creates the need for information (Uhegbu, 2007). Human and societal needs are varied; some needs are close to the solution of problems at hand and are considered relevant. There are various needs (using Maslow's Hierarchy of needs theory), such as the need for food, shelter, thirst, sex, (physiological), security and protection (safety), love/affection, belongingness, acceptance (social), self-respect, autonomy, achievement, power, status, recognition, etc. (self-esteem-internal and external), and drive for growth, achieving one's potential, self-fulfillment (self-actualization) (Robbins, 1983; Iheriohanma, 2002). Every information need is based on what is critically relevant to a need at a time. This makes it imperative to select, draw priority scale of preference and the information needs must be processed and analyzed. To this end, information need analysis becomes a process of identifying, collating and critically evaluating the needed information, ideas and knowledge in a community or other defined population for application and use in a circumstance or situation.

In a related circumstance, intelligence refers to information gathered clandestinely or overtly, regarding the economic, political, social, religious, military, strategic conditions, and the accurate, complete and timely background information

and intentions in relation to the foreign policy and national defense of the ruling leaders of a particular country or other climes (Borosage & Marks, 1976). The above definition implies that intelligence revolves around nations and foreign matters regarding, but not limited to, military and defense. Intelligence is inclusive of all activities and information of various individuals and groups considered to pose threats or inimical to national security. In our circumstance here, individuals and groups would include terrorist groups, herdsmen, Boko Haram, Islamic sects, ethnic militia groups, religious sectarian groups whose activities are by law, considered inimical to the existence and security of a country. Gill (2014) observes that intelligence involves secret activities, targeting, collation, analysis, evaluation, dissemination, integration, interpretation of available information and actions intended to boost security and or maintain power relative to competitors aimed at forewarning of threats and gaining of opportunities. Intelligence involves surveillance, information, knowledge and has links with action, power, policy, strategy, security and resistance. It does not just refer to external but includes internal surveillance.

Security refers to a people's freedom from any harm, threat or violence which, if left unmitigated, could result to *"loss of lives and properties"* (Adeleke, 2013). United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (1994) defines human security as the protection of the citizens from unforeseen and *"harmful disruption from their daily activities, at homes, offices or communities"*. Security in this investigation, is the freedom people have from threat to their existence, harm, fear, diseases, squalor living, unemployment, marginalization, discrimination, human rights violations, latitude to undertake appropriate actions without hindrances especially in the areas of socio-political, economic, educational, etc. desires and attainment, development and achievement of capacities, etc. within a sovereign nation such as Nigeria. The presence or infringement of these implies insecurity.

1.2 The Challenging Problems of Study

In a security conscious nation, there is need for security agencies whose primary functions include but not excluded of systematic and systemic collection and collation of information, evaluation and analysis of such information on continuous regular basis and processing them into intelligence, imploring swift pro-active actions and dissemination of the intelligence information to where they are relevantly and urgently needed, the protection of such intelligence information from leaking into the hands of intelligence operatives of other competitors and continuous surveillance of the nation's borders and intellectual property and patency. These functions indicate four strategic areas of importance: strategic, tactical, pro-activity and counter intelligence. From the above, it implies that intelligence is dependent on information while information is a critical value of intelligence. Without information, intelligence is void, and without intelligence, information is crippled.

The level and regularity of insecurity in Nigeria presently, and by extension, Third World countries and in fact, all over the world, poses series of problems and

questions that need to be examined. The incessant and constant insecurity overshadowing the citizenry, lives and properties of Nigerians appears to suggest questioning the existence of government and or its ability to exercise its constitutional roles. The role of government anywhere is the protection of lives and property of the citizenry. The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, section 14 (2) (b) states inter alia that *“the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of the government”*. Unfortunately, no day passes by without the mention of kidnapping, bombing, killings, economic and politically related assassinations, insurgence, insurrection, etc. The Arab Spring that engulfed North African countries (Tunisia, Egypt, Libya, etc.) between 2014 and 2016; the California school shooting in February, 2018; the Boko Haram incidences in Nigeria since far back as 2009/2010 till date, and which have directly and indirectly affected Nigeria’s neighbours of Cameroun, Chad, Niger Republic, etc.; the Borno Chibok School Girls abduction from Government Girls Secondary School, Chibok on 14 April 2014 where about two hundred and seventy-six girls were abducted (only few of them have been released and about one hundred and twelve are still being held in captivity as at the time of this research) and more recently the 19th February, 2018 Dapchi Government Girls’ Science Technical College, Yobe state where about a hundred and ten girls were abducted and one hundred and four ‘returned’ on the 22nd March, 2018 (only Leah Sharibu is still held hostage because she refused to renounce her Christian faith); the Fulani Herdsmen-Farmers clashes that have every now and again resonated and reverberated in Nigeria for a very long time now and which have engulfed villages and local government areas like Guma, Agatu, Zaki Biam, etc in Benue State and other states such as Kaduna, Nassarawa, Anambra, Plateau, Enugu (Ukpabi-Nimbo), Yobe, Adamawa, Abia, Kogi; the Bayelsa state (Odii) and Benue state (Zaki Biam) incidences under Obasanjo’s regime; the Aguleri – Umuleri clashes in Anambra state; the Ezaa - Ezilo in Ebonyi state land dispute; the constant boundary clashes between Ebonyi and Cross River states, etc.; and the Omoku Rivers state killings of first January, 2018 by cult members; the terrorists bombings especially the Henry Okah bombing of Abuja on Independence Day, 2010; the Nyanya Bus Terminal bomb blast on 14 April 2014 (terror attack); the Offa, Kwara state bank robbery on April 5, 2018 that took the lives of seven police officers and twenty-six others (for which the state governor Ahmed Fatai and the Senate President Bukola Saraki are being quizzed); the 24th April, 2018 Fulani herdsmen unleashed terror on Ayar Mbalom community in the Gwer East L. G. A. of Benue State killing nineteen (19) persons including two Catholic Revered Fathers – Joseph Gor and Felix Tyolaha; the unaccounted unending lists of kidnappings and espionages; the Maitatsine riots in the Northern states led by Muhammadu Marwa a Cameroonian in Nigeria) between 1980 - 1985; the killing of T. M. Yusuf (Ustaz Mohammed Yusuf) on 30 July, 2009; the Shi’ite group – Islamic Movement of Nigeria (IMN) - and police clash in Abuja starting from 15 April, 2018 and which sporadically is lasting for days because of the continued detention of their leader, Sheik Ibrahim El-Zakzaky; the incessant gunmen attacks on daily basis; cattle rustling; the constant bombings of Boko Haram insurgents of flash

points, etc. are but a tip of the examples of the insecurity situations in Nigeria and elsewhere.

The irate consistency and regularity with which the insecurity occurs, the rapidity with which foreign investors fold their businesses out of fear and or relocate to neighbouring countries where they supposedly find conducive investment environment, the inability of the government of the day to curtail the terrific and horrifying death toll from the violence/insecurity, the complicity involved in government handling of security issues any time there is need to soothe the nerves of the public with security information and needed proactive actions, the regularity with which defense and security vehicles blare their siren on the roads, harass and intimidate innocent citizens on daily basis, the inability of the agencies, especially the police to respond to distress calls, the reactive instead of pro-active response of the security agencies to insecurity issues, the glaring eroded public confidence on the police with respect to provision of security and intelligent information and management of security situations, the seemingly non-collaborative and synergic relationship between security agencies in Nigeria, the inability of security agencies to detect crime before its machination, etc., all these suggest the inability of government to secure lives and property of the citizenry – the main constitutional duty of government - as well as a glaring evidence that the security outfits have failed. These, and more, are some of the challenging problems of this investigation. The worrisome aspect is that public funds are allocated, through the budgets and extra budgetary provisions, to the ministries and institutions in-charge of the security agencies that appear to have been involved in dereliction of their constitutional duties. Among the agitating problematic questions in this paper are: Is the incessant insecurity in Nigeria in particular a result of lack of information and intelligence needs gathering and analysis? Are the ineffectiveness and inefficiency of the security agencies to combat the terrifying level of insecurity in the land a result of challenges in availing themselves the apparatus for effective information and intelligence needs gathering, analysis, sharing and utilization? Are there no collaborative efforts between the various security agencies in Nigeria? What should be done to leverage the efforts of these agencies to firmly execute their statutory constitutional roles to secure lives and property in Nigeria in particular? These, and more, form the guiding questions from where the objectives for investigation in the study are derived.

The general objective of this paper is to discursively and analytically investigate the synergic relationship between effective information and intelligence needs analysis and utilization in relation to insecurity situation in Nigeria. While it is analytical, discursive and integrative, the methodology is devoid of empirical field research characteristic of social science investigations of this nature.

2. Security, Effective Information and Intelligence Needs Gathering and Analysis

It would be preposterous to ask if a country like Nigeria, with multi-ethnic, multi-religious, multi-lingual, porous borders, preponderance of unemployed youths, under-employed population, large expanse of land, and patrimonial inclinations requires effective information, intelligence needs assessment, analysis, articulation, information sharing among its security forces. Information is power. No nation is security free or has a tight border to the extent that citizens always go to bed at night with their two eyes tightly closed. Even the developed countries of America, Britain, Germany, China, Japan, etc. still continue to upgrade their security details and apparatuses on daily basis. They always think and plan ahead of security foes who, they suspect, would always try to be ahead of them by attempting to puncture every move in surveillance. Nigeria's security issues are at the exclusive list in the constitution, with the state governors as the security chiefs of their respective states. They have the leverage to formulate policies and institute structures to ensure effective security. They are allocated security votes to this effect. The definitions on intelligence by both Borosage and Marks (1976) and Gills (2014) indicate the necessity of every independent nation to continually articulate, collate, analyze, disseminate, etc. information gathered for intelligence for the protection of its external and internal territory and for making available such intelligence information to where they are relevantly and urgently needed. The nation also protects such intelligence information from leaking to other competitors. It protects such intellectual property and patency with tenacity. The essence is to uphold the tenacious functions of the four strategic areas of importance such as strategic, tactical, pro-active and counter intelligence areas. The reason for effective intelligence information needs is to counter any seemingly aggressive invasion from foes and enemies. If Nigeria upholds the intelligence information needs analysis theory, it would be difficult for it to fail in counter terrorism and in its fight against corruption. Every independent nation now is involved in digitalization of information communication technology (ICT) and security gadgets, jettisoning analogue military and security weapons and equipment and training and retraining of its security personnel.

3. Challenges Facing Information and Intelligence Needs among Security Agencies in Nigeria

The observed level of insecurity and constancy with which lives and properties are lost on daily basis, coupled with the frequencies with which foreign investors are relocating out of Nigeria to other neighbouring countries suggest that the security agencies are facing lots of challenges. The governments of Nigeria since the inception of democratic rule in 1979 have consistently allocated and released resources (financial, human and equipment) to defense and security measures, yet much leaves to be desired. The notable security agencies whose duties are to secure the internal and external territorial

boundaries in Nigeria include the military force/soldiers (army, navy and air force), State Security Service and other secret intelligence agencies, the Police Force, the Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC), the Nigeria Intelligence Agency (NIA), the Customs and Immigration services, and more recently, the various vigilante groups operating under the creation and watchful eyes of some state governments.

There are a lot of challenges and obstacles facing intelligence and information needs among security agencies in Nigeria (Nte, 2012). These include but not limited to the under-listed factors. To say the least, they account for the reasons for the ineffectiveness of the security agencies.

- a. The apparent non-existent or collaborative efforts among the intelligence agencies on information seeking, analysis and sharing with respect to crime detection.
- b. Ineffective operating laws on information sharing between intelligence agencies, and where such exist, they are not enforced as a result of poor political will.
- c. Individualism, secretive nature and isolationism among the agencies.
- d. Lack of patriotism and ineptitude by officers of intelligence and security agencies in Nigeria. This is an offshoot of colonial heritage and leadership ineptitude in Nigeria.
- e. Lack of synergism in the articulation processes in intelligence generation, gathering, analysis and sharing.
- f. Inability of intelligence officials to protect informants on criminal information and even in the discharge of their duties. This has affected the posture and trust of, especially the police in Nigeria. Citizens find it difficult to thrust the efficiency of the police in particular to protect them. This may have been one of the reasons for the formation of certain ethnic militia, the Bakasi Boys, the Egbesu group, the Joint Task Force (JTF) in the North-East, etc. as alternative and complementary to government security agencies.
- g. Porous Nigerian borders. This is the effect of poor leadership, governance and corruption and which have surreptitiously affected and infected the customs, immigration and all institutional structures and economy in Nigeria.
- h. Poor economic situation under which agency officials hide for nefarious activities. There is hardly any serious surveillance, control and sincerity of purpose by any officer, especially the police and customs, as a result of the above excuse. Officials of security agencies always complain of paucity of funds and or equipment, using it as excuses for poor response to distress calls. Again, police officers have used this as excuse to justify their extortion of motorists at road blocks, saying they use the money proceeds for vehicle maintenance. All the Inspector Generals of Police (IGPs) have always closed their eyes to public complaints on this, indicating tacit connivance to this act.
- i. Lack of functional modern equipment to do effective ground, air and sea surveillance. Digitalization rather than analogue equipment and updated modern security gadgets with ICT are the in-thing now as crime and criminality

have gone nuclear. Unfortunately, where some of the equipment, especially ICT equipped vehicles are procured they hardly last, maintained, etc., and at times, the officers use them recklessly.

The level of insecurity suggests that government of Nigeria is only involved in the procurement of equipment and misapplication of defense and security forces in the name of securing the nation. A situation where a notable politician is allotted up to five police officers guiding him alone while the rest of the masses are left at the mercy of armed bandits is deplorable and unacceptable. It could be suggested that government rather concentrates on the factors that generate the need to deploy and misapply security forces. Government and especially the Inspector General of Police (IGP) have on several occasions directed that these attached police officers be reassigned to areas of need but the decisions are quickly reversed. The recent sporadic shooting on 2nd June, 2018 at the flag – off of the All Progressive Congress, Ekiti state gubernatorial candidate's rally is a case in point. Lives were lost and many wounded. The factors bedeviling the nation for now include poverty, youth unemployment (Ezema 2016), poor entrepreneurship and empowerment, low level of human and capacity development even among the security agencies, dilapidated infrastructure, low technological development for military hardware especially in information communication technology (ICT) for satellite surveillance, information and intelligence seeking, articulation and synthesizing, etc., inconsistent and unstable policies, inequality, ethnic chauvinism and abuse of human rights. These call for urgent rectification and building of structures to enable economic boom for job creation, enabling environment for entrepreneurship, capacity building, good governance to enlist the interest and patriotism of the citizens, especially the youths that do not see any light at the end of the tunnel.

4. Reasons for Incessant Insecurity in Nigeria

The exploration of why Nigeria is witnessing incessant insecurity indicates that a country with poor leadership, political intolerance, poor governance, human right abuses, inequity in sharing the commonwealth, constitutional infringement, overwhelming youth unemployment, poor human capacity building and development (Iheriohanma, 2006), marginalization, religious intolerance, ethnic chauvinism, strong personalities and politicians as against strong institutional structures for governance, etc. cannot boast of complacency and healthy living among its citizens.

The forms and reasons or causes of insecurity in Nigeria could be classified thus: *political factors* which include the unexpected power shift from the oligarchic North to the South-South with the confirmation of Goodluck Ebele Jonathan as the Head of State and Commander in Chief of the Armed Forces following the hospitalization and subsequent death of President Musa Yar'Adua in 2010. This heightened the tempo of insecurity in Nigeria. Following the above is the alteration of power rotation or shift between Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) and All Progressives Congress (APC),

political assassinations and political rancor within and between opposing political parties (Adeleke, 2013). *Leadership factor and poor governance* relate to the fact that Nigeria has been bedeviled with oppressive, selfish, directionless and corrupt leaders whose interest is in the looting of government treasury rather than selfless serving leaders for development (Achebe, 1998). This accounts for the poor governance experienced in Nigeria especially since the advent of military dictators and dethronement of nationalists who labored to gain independence for Nigeria. *Unemployment rate and youth population* have rather created cancerous disease in the economic and management institutions in Nigeria. It is a truism that an idle mind creates room for mischief. The rising rate of unemployment, especially among the youth population is alarming as Ogah, Fanimu, Shadare, Ebosele, Okere, Adepetun, and Lawrence (2011) quoted the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS) putting the figure at 23.9%. This figure is still going up as the Nigerian government and leadership are making no desperate effort at checkmating the rising increase. Every year the number of youth job seekers continues to skyrocket with the institutions of higher learning churning out fresh graduates. The effects on the economy, society and security at large are better imagined. Available job vacant positions are reserved for one's cronies or the highest bidders. At times, monies transfer hands, yet the jobs are not secured (Ogah *et al.*, 2013). The Nigerian Immigration Service (NIS), the Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC) and the Nigeria Peace Corp job racketing are but examples. *Corruption* is not only in government offices, institutions, ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs). It has permeated all facets of human living in the Nigerian society. Where there are poor governance occasioned by insensitive and inept leadership, strong personalities rather than strong institutions to regulate activities, there is bound to be corruption, marginalization, brigandry, favouritism, arson, negligence, etc. and all these breed grounds for acrimony among citizens and the resultant effects are on the security of the land. *Economic and Psychological Factors:* Attendant to the above are increased poverty, decayed and dilapidated infrastructure, out migration as evidenced in the number of youth that left the shores of Nigeria for Libya in search of greener pastures, dislocation of societal values resulting to *anomie* and suicide, high illiteracy level and continued school drop-outs. The fragrant and ostentatious lifestyles of our politicians agitate the minds of the poor and the educated youth who are either used as tugs during electioneering campaigns, cult activities, ballot box snatching, etc. and who watch helplessly against the unfulfilled promises of these politicians. These anomic situations have over-bearing effects on the security agencies and personnel who are over-burdened and appear ineffective and ill-equipped with both information and requisite intelligence to carry out their legitimate security assignments. Again, living in Nigeria without economic source of livelihood is an invitation to suicide.

5. The Exigency for Collaborative Efforts among Security Agencies in Nigeria

Ugoanochie (2003) stressed the need for security consciousness in man, as human beings can only be comfortable and at peace when their lives and prosperities are adequately secured against natural and man-made disasters. Generally, security is regarded as the condition of being protected from danger. Security devices are designed to guide people's lives, properties, guard crime, sabotage, and accident; protect humans from clandestine, overt, covert hurtful disruptions; protections from danger to enhance citizens' freedom, fulfillment in the pursuance of valued political, economic and social ambitions. Security is essentially a veritable part of the socio-economic and political life. It is a measure to protect life in any given human society and for the economy to thrive. Without adequate security, foreign and even domestic investors cannot be attracted. Eventually, economy cannot grow.

To this end, it requires the exigency for the various security agencies in Nigeria to collaborate with each other in the areas of intrinsic and extrinsic secretiveness as it is done in security conscious nations all over the world. The outputs in security studies and reviews are for collaborations among the agencies. Inputs and outcomes of intelligence studies are primarily not for hoarding by any agencies except for extremely intrinsic and critical purposes (Parkes, 2017). Funds for intelligence research, investigation and information gathering, analysis and dissemination can always be set up either centrally or within the domains of each agency and should be readily accessed when need arises. Information and intelligence data sets and banks are critical for successful security pursuits for improving intelligence gathering, analysis, storage and use. Collaboration encourages trade-off between the collection, storage, analysis and use especially in what Bwanson & Vogel (2017) called "large unclassified data-sets and analysis" relating to privacy challenges. This prevails more in privacy concerns, future big data and research center analysis that collaborate with intelligence communities. To this end, insecurity could be minimized and the citizens can build their lives and pursue their legitimate social, economic and political activities without hindrances. Collaboration between security agencies encourages countering of activities of insurgents as sharing of intelligence information among security agencies provides for proactive counter-force and pre-empting espionages, insecurity and actions of enemies of peace instead of rhetoric and blames as is the case in Nigeria.

6. Conclusion

The investigation is on the synergy in the relationship between effective information and intelligence needs analysis, utilization and security in Nigeria. Nigeria has experienced incessant security challenges, especially since inception of democratic rule in 1999. This study examined why the recurrent insecurity and observed that there are a lot of factors ranging from political, leadership, poor governance, unemployment rate and rising youth population, corruption, economic and psychological factors. The

investigation explored the challenges facing security agencies and their ineffectiveness in the areas of information and intelligence needs analysis and gathering and decried the existence and use of analogue rather than digitalized modern equipment, low military hardware equipment use and development, poor funding, corruption and poor synergic and collaborative relationship among security personnel in crime detection. The exigency for collaborative efforts was also examined and it reiterated on pro-active rather than reactive policing in crime detection, prevention and control, decried 'individualism' and isolationism among the agencies. Collaboration counters the activities of insurgents as sharing and dissemination of intelligence information fortifies and fosters efficiency among the agencies.

7. Recommendations for Leveraging the Efforts of Security Agencies towards Effective Information and Intelligence Needs Analysis and Utilization in Nigeria

The following are recommended to leverage the efforts of security agencies in Nigeria for effective information and intelligence needs analysis and utilization.

- Funds for intelligence research, investigation and information gathering analysis and dissemination should be set up either centrally or within the domains of each agency and accessed as at when need arises. This also gives rise to setting up information and intelligence data sets and banks critical for successful security pursuits for improving intelligence gathering, analysis, storage and use.
- Collaborative efforts among the intelligence agencies on intelligence and information seeking, analysis and sharing should be emphasized. Effective operating laws on information sharing between intelligence agencies are now a necessity. There should be the political will to ensure the enforcement of the laws and operations. There is no need for individualism, secretive nature and isolationism among the agencies.
- Functional, modern and digitalized equipment to do effective ground, air and sea surveillance are recommended. Updated modern security gadgets with ICT are a necessity now as crime and criminality have gone nuclear. Mounting of close circuit televisions at strategic places, public buildings, etc. is now a necessity.
- In international circles, Nigeria has out-grown the experience and use of low technological development for military hardware especially in information communication technology (ICT) for satellite surveillance, information and intelligence seeking, articulation and synthesizing, etc. Efforts should be geared towards production and or procurement of sophisticated military hardware for ground, air, water and satellite surveillance, etc. Inconsistent and unstable policies of successive governments in this regard are decried because national interest is paramount.
- Collaboration between security agencies demobilizes counter-activities of insurgents. Sharing of intelligence information among security agencies

provides for proactive counter-force, counter-insurgency and pre-empts espionage, insecurity and actions of enemies, both internal and external. Government should constantly embark on training and retraining of its security personnel to be abreast of use of modern and digitalized security equipment. These forestall rhetoric and blames always experienced in Nigeria.

- To leverage the burden on the security agencies on crime and criminality, especially among the youth, government must create enabling environment for human capacity building, job creation, empowerment, entrepreneurship, enterprises and opportunities for the citizens to realize their potentials and the economy to grow. Minimization of crime and criminality presents opportunity for both the individuals, institutions and government to explore grounds for technological, economic and political development and excellence.

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